

SYNTHESIS OF NEW LOCAL ANAESTHETICS. PART II

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Piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-4-phenyl-, -4-*p*-chlorophenyl-, -4-*p*-aminophenyl-, -4-methyl-, -4-chloromethyl-, -4:5-dimethyl- and -4-methyl-5-ethyl-thiazoles have been synthesised and their local anaesthetic activity tested. The hydrochlorides of piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-4-methyl-5-ethyl- -4-*p*-chlorophenyl- and -4-*p*-aminophenyl-thiazoles have been found to be active local anaesthetics.

In continuation of the previous work (Bhargava and Nair, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 42), 2-amino-4-phenyl-, -4-*p*-chlorophenyl-, -4-*p*-aminophenyl- -4-methyl-, -4-chloromethyl-, -4:5-dimethyl- and -4-methyl-5-ethyl-thiazoles were prepared as the starting materials, which were in the first stage condensed with chloroacetyl chloride to obtain the corresponding chloroacetylamino compounds. These were further condensed with a secondary amine, piperidine. The hydrochlorides of these bases have been prepared and their local anaesthetic activity has been tested by frog's sciatic plexus method.

A study of the pharmacological screening (Bulbring and Wajda, *J. Pharmacol.*, 1945, 85, 78) shows that the hydrochlorides of piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-4-methyl-5-ethyl-, -4-*p*-chlorophenyl- and -4-*p*-aminophenyl-thiazoles are the most active of these compounds. The values obtained for these are less than that for procaine hydrochloride. It is found that an extra amino group and a chlorine atom in *para* position in the benzene nucleus confer more activity on the compound than the presence of a higher aromatic nucleus. The simple benzene nucleus enhances the solubility and volatility of the compound as compared with other condensed rings.

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2-Amino-4 or 4:5-substituted thiazoles were prepared according to the method of Dodson and King (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2242). Properties and analytical data of these are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

2-Aminothiazoles.

[T denotes thiazole. A denotes 2-amino-].

	Compounds.	% Yield.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
						Found.	Calc.
1.	A-4-phenyl-T*	68	Yellow	147°	C ₉ H ₈ N ₂ S	19.35	19.94
2.	A-4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-T†	70	"	164°	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ ClS	15.03	15.13
3.	A-4- <i>p</i> -aminophenyl-T†	72	"	174°	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ S	16.70	16.75
4.	A-4-methyl-T*	56	Brown	126°	C ₇ H ₈ N ₂ S	27.85	28.06
5.	A-4-chloromethyl-T	52	"	123°	C ₈ H ₈ N ₂ ClS	17.10	17.17
6.	A-4:5-dimethyl-T	48	"	131°	C ₈ H ₉ N ₂ S	24.85	25.00
7.	A-4-methyl-5-ethyl-T	36	"	135°	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₂ S	22.30	22.33

* Dodson and King, *loc. cit.*† King and Hlaveck, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 3722.

Chloroacetyl-2-amino-4-phenylthiazole.—Chloroacetyl chloride (13 c.c.), dissolved in dry benzene (12 c.c.), was gradually added to 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole (5 g.), dissolved in benzene (30 c.c.). The reaction mixture was warmed at 70° on a water-bath for 1½ hours. Benzene was distilled off and the residue washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, then with water, and dried. The product was crystallised from alcohol in light yellow crystals, m.p. 157°

Other chloroacetyl-2-aminothiazoles were similarly prepared. Properties and analytical data of these are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Chloroacetyl-2-aminothiazoles.

Compound.	% Yield.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	% Chlorine.	
					Found.	Calc.
1. -A-4-phenyl-T	72	Light yellow	157°	C ₁₁ H ₉ ON ₂ ClS	13.92	14.06
2. -A-4-p-chlorophenyl-T	78	Do	118°	C ₁₁ H ₈ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	24.00	24.39
3. -A-4-p-aminophenyl-T	82	Yellowish green	187°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ON ₂ ClS	13.42	13.27
4. -A-4-methyl-T	68	Brown	211°	C ₈ H ₇ ON ₂ ClS	18.94	19.06
5. -A-4-chloromethyl-T	64	Brownish black	121°	C ₈ H ₆ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	31.08	31.11
6. -A-4:5-dimethyl-T	71	Brown	119°	C ₇ H ₉ ON ₂ ClS	17.25	17.38
7. -A-4-methyl-5-ethyl-T	65	Do	120°	C ₉ H ₁₁ ON ₂ ClS	16.32	16.40

Piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-4-phenylthiazole.—To chloroacetyl-2-amino-4-phenylthiazole (5 g.) in absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) piperidine (3.5 c.c.) was added and the mixture refluxed for 4 to 5 hours. Alcohol and excess of piperidine were recovered by distillation and the residue was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The product was crystallised from 50% alcohol and recrystallised from benzene in brown crystals, m.p. 167°. Similarly piperidinoacetyl derivatives of other 2-aminothiazoles were prepared. Their properties and analytical data are shown in Table III

TABLE III

Piperidinoacetyl-2-aminothiazoles and their hydrochlorides.

No.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	* Piperidino derivatives of compounds.		Hydrochlorides		
				% Sulphur.		M.P.	% Chlorine.	
				Found.	Calc.			Found.
1.	Brown	167°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ S	10.75	10.97	254°	10.92	11.04
2.	Do	109°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ ClS	9.85	10.00	130°	19.06	19.56
3.	Do	152°	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₄ S	10.50	10.67	245°	10.43	10.69
4.	Brownish black	114°	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	14.26	14.35	119°	13.50	13.71
5.	Do	107°	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ N ₃ ClS	12.30	12.44	165°	23.25	23.86
6.	Black	132°	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ S	13.45	13.50	153°	12.65	12.98
7.	Do	109°	C ₁₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ S	12.50	12.75	123°	13.50	13.71

* The related compounds as recorded in Table II.

Pharmacological screening.—The hydrochlorides of 2-amino-4 or 4:5-substituted thiazoles were screened for local anaesthetic activity by frog's sciatic test. Two frogs were tested for each compound in 0.1 and 0.2% concentration and the time taken by a given concentration of local anaesthetic to fail to provoke withdrawal of foot was recorded. The results are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Results of local anaesthesia.

Hydrochlorides.	Onset of anaesthesia in		Onset of anaesthesia	
	0.1N-HCl.	0.2N-HCl.	0.1N-HCl.	0.2N-HCl.
	A. Conc. of anaesthesia = 0.1%.		B. Conc. of anaesthesia = 0.2%.	
1. Procaine	15 mins.	20 mins.	12 mins.	14 mins.
2. Pa-A-4-phenyl-T	16	20	13	16
3. Pa-A-4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-T	10	14	9	12
4. Pa-A-4- <i>p</i> -aminophenyl-T	12	15	10	13
5. Pa-A-4-methyl-T	17	22	15	18
6. Pa-A-4-chloromethyl-T	14	17	13	15
7. Pa-A-4:5-dimethyl-T	13	16	12	13
8. Pa-A-4-methyl-5-ethyl-T	10	14	8	10

N.B. Pa stands for piperidinoacetyl.

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